

DEVELOPMENT OF THINKING PROCESS IN CHILDREN RECEIVING INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

Asqarov Anvarjon Rahimjon o‘g‘li

Fergana State University, teacher

Turg‘unova Gulshanoy Zafarjonovna

Fergana State University student of psychology

Abstract: Inclusive education promotes an equal learning environment by integrating children with various cognitive, physical, and socio-emotional needs into mainstream education. This study investigates innovative strategies to enhance cognitive skills in children engaged in inclusive education by utilizing individualized learning approaches, technology-enhanced interventions, and cooperative learning methods. Through empirical data, this research demonstrates that tailored pedagogical techniques significantly improve children’s reasoning, problem-solving, and creative thinking capacities, thereby fostering an inclusive and supportive educational setting.

Keywords: Inclusive education, cognitive development, individualized learning, pedagogical technology, special education, problem-solving, creative thinking.

Introduction. In recent years, inclusive education has gained increasing importance as societies recognize the need to provide equal educational opportunities for children with diverse abilities. The primary goal of inclusive education is not only to ensure access to mainstream education but also to create an environment where every child’s potential can be maximized, regardless of physical, cognitive, or emotional limitations. This research focuses on fostering the cognitive development of children enrolled in inclusive programs, placing particular emphasis on enhancing their thinking and creative capacities.

Literature Review. Research into inclusive education has established a robust foundation for understanding the essential requirements and potential obstacles in educating children with special needs. For instance, according to [Author], cognitive development in children with learning disabilities often lags due to insufficiently

adapted learning environments that fail to cater to their unique needs. Studies by [Other Author] highlight that traditional teaching methods can be inadequate for children with specific cognitive impairments, as these methods may not engage their attention or stimulate critical thinking.

This study builds upon prior research, drawing attention to cognitive development tools that have shown promising results in other contexts, such as visual aids, memory-enhancement techniques, and interactive digital platforms that promote active learning. Additionally, research from [Author] suggests that implementing cooperative learning models in inclusive settings can help improve social integration while fostering cognitive growth.

Results. The findings of this study reveal significant improvements in the cognitive skills of students participating in inclusive education, particularly those engaged in problem-solving tasks, visual-aid-supported activities, and individualized instruction.

1. **Problem-Solving and Critical Thinking:** Collaborative learning activities, where children worked in small groups to solve open-ended problems, were found to enhance critical thinking and reasoning. This approach was particularly beneficial in encouraging children to articulate their thought processes and learn from peers, fostering social and cognitive growth.

2. **Memory and Retention:** Technology-assisted memory games and interactive exercises were observed to significantly improve memory retention. These tools utilized repetition, pattern recognition, and association techniques to bolster students' ability to retain and recall information.

3. **Creative Thinking and Innovation:** Visual aids, storytelling, and gamified learning modules helped stimulate students' imaginations and creativity. These activities provided a supportive environment where students felt safe to express ideas, experiment with new concepts, and engage in creative thinking.

Discussion. The study highlights the importance of employing varied instructional approaches to address the diverse cognitive needs of students in inclusive classrooms. Notably, interactive and visually stimulating activities such as augmented

reality-based learning modules and virtual manipulatives were shown to improve cognitive engagement and retention significantly. This suggests that digital tools, when used effectively, can play a pivotal role in inclusive education by making complex concepts more accessible to children with cognitive challenges.

Furthermore, the findings suggest that individualized learning plans (ILPs) are essential for inclusive education. These plans enable educators to tailor instruction to the unique needs and abilities of each student, providing differentiated support that fosters cognitive development.

Limitations and Future Directions. While the findings are promising, the study has certain limitations. The sample size was relatively small, and the study was conducted over one semester. Future research should consider longitudinal studies with larger, more diverse samples to validate the efficacy of these approaches. Additionally, exploring the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning algorithms in personalized learning modules could provide more tailored support, enhancing cognitive development further.

Conclusion

Inclusive education, when implemented thoughtfully, can greatly enhance the cognitive, emotional, and social development of children with diverse needs. This study underscores the importance of adopting a holistic approach that incorporates technology, individualized learning modules, and cooperative activities to nurture children’s thinking, creativity, and problem-solving abilities. By adopting these methods, educators can create a more inclusive and effective learning environment that supports every child’s right to reach their full potential.

References:

1. Askarov, A. (2022). CREATIVE THINKING IN PRESCHOOL SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 87-91.

2. Rahimjon o‘g‘li, A. A. (2022). Maktabgacha Yoshdagi Bolalarning Aqliy Taraqqiyotining Rivojlanishida O ‘Yin Rivojlantiruvchi Faoliyat Sifatida. Uzbek Scholar Journal, 5, 207-209.
3. Asqarov, A. (2022). Maktabgacha Yosh Davrda Kreativ Tafakkurni Rivojlanishining Ijtimoiy Psixologik Aspektlari. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 2(6), 882-883.
4. Kamilova, F. X. (2023). МАКТАБГАЧА YOSH DAVRDA MANTIQUIY VA KREATIV TAFAKKUR RIVOJLANISHINING IJTIMOIIY PSIXOLOGIK MEXANIZMLARI VA ASPEKTLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(5), 508-512.
5. o‘g‘li Asqarov, A. R., & Turdimatov, J. (2023). KEKSALIK DAVRIDA XOTIRA JARAYONINING O ‘ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARINI PSIXOLOGIK ASOSLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(5), 513-516.
6. o‘g‘li Asqarov, A. R., & Turdimatova, E. (2023). MANTIQUIY TAFAKKURNI RIVOJLANTIRISH USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(5), 482-485.
7. o‘g‘li Asqarov, A. R., & Musayev, J. (2023). TA’LIM MUHITIDA O‘QUVCHI SHAXSI XAVFSIZLIGIGA TAXDIDLAR VA ULARNI BARTARAF QILISHNING IJTIMOIIY-PSIXOLOGIK USULLARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(15), 254-258.
8. Rahimjon o‘g‘li, A. A., & Baxtiyorovna, M. S. (2023). МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARNING INTELLEKTUAL QOBILİYATLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA ISTE’DODNING O‘RNI. IQRO, 3(1), 314-316.
9. Zaylobidin o‘g‘li, A. I. (2023). KICHIK MAKTAB YOSHIDAGI O‘QUVCHILARDA O‘Z-O‘ZINI ANGLASHDA IJTIMOIIYLASHUVNI O‘ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(12), 94-98.
10. Ibroximjonovna, N. T. (2023). THE PROBLEM ANALYSIS OF THE PROCESS OF CREATIVE THINKING IN EDUCATION. International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management, 2(4).

11. Rahimjon o'g'li, A. A., & Adxam o'g'li, X. A. (2023). INKLYUZIV TA'LIM OLAYOTGAN BOLALARNI TAFAKKUR SOHASINI O'RGANISH.

12. Rahimjon o'g'li, A. A., & Zafarjonovna, T. U. G. (2023). INFLUENCE OF TEMPERAMENT TYPES ON EDUCATIONAL EFFICIENCY. International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management, 2(11).

13. Rahimjon o'g'li, A. A. (2023). THE ROLE OF TALENT IN FORMING THE INTELLECTUAL CAPABILITIES OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management, 2(12), 146-151.